

Model Fragility Beyond Base Correlation: An Operator-Theoretic Approach to CDO Risk Measurement

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Abstract

Base correlation, the industry-standard measure of copula model risk for collateralized debt obligations, is structurally blind to an entire dimension of parameter sensitivity. We establish this blindness as a mathematical theorem and develop an operator-theoretic framework that captures the missing information.

The CDO pricing operator is defined as an integral operator on $L^2([0, 1])$ whose kernel is the conditional tranche loss function. We prove its Fréchet differentiability and define the *conduction intensity* τ as the operator norm of the derivative. A duality theorem shows that τ equals the first-order growth rate of local parametric model uncertainty in the sense of Cont [3], with explicit second-order corrections. Three functional independence theorems then establish that τ and base correlation carry provably distinct information: the Jacobian of the map $(\beta, p) \mapsto (\rho_{\text{base}}, \tau)$ has rank two, with the root cause traced to an amplification factor $1/\varphi(\Phi^{-1}(p))$ entering τ but invisible to ρ_{base} .

A phase transition theorem shows that senior tranche τ jumps from near-zero to $O(1)$ at a critical parameter curve. A granularity analysis reveals that the large homogeneous pool approximation overestimates τ in normal markets but underestimates it in crisis, with the scale factor varying by nearly 50% across parameters. Numerical experiments on 1,600 parameter configurations confirm that at identical base correlation levels, τ varies by over 150-fold.

Keywords: CDO pricing, model risk, copula, conduction intensity, phase transition, base correlation, operator theory, model uncertainty

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1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The Gaussian copula model of [15] became the industry standard for pricing collateralized debt obligations (CDOs) during the 2000s. Its central assumption—that default dependence among reference entities can be captured by a single correlation parameter—proved inadequate during the crisis of 2007–2009, when senior tranches suffered losses exceeding 60% of notional. The subsequent growth of the CLO (collateralized loan obligation) market to over \$1 trillion in outstanding notional by 2024, priced using similar copula frameworks, has renewed interest in quantifying the fragility of these models.

Existing CDO risk metrics—base correlation, tranche delta, CDX index spread—are scalar compressions of the copula parameter space. They discard information about which parameter perturbations are most dangerous and which tranches are most vulnerable. This paper develops an operator-theoretic framework that preserves the full directional structure and demonstrates, both theoretically and numerically, that it captures information provably absent from base correlation.

1.2 Overview

We define the CDO pricing operator \mathcal{P}_θ and prove its Fréchet differentiability (§3). The operator norm of the derivative—the conduction intensity τ —measures worst-case parameter sensitivity (§4). A duality theorem identifies τ as the first-order growth rate of local model uncertainty in the sense of [3], with a computable second-order correction (§5). A phase transition theorem characterizes the abrupt activation of senior tranche fragility (§6). Three functional independence theorems prove $\tau \neq g(\rho_{\text{base}})$ (§7). A granularity analysis quantifies the bias of the large homogeneous pool (LHP) approximation (§9), and systematic numerical experiments validate all predictions (§10).

1.3 Related literature

The CDO pricing literature, initiated by [15] and extended by [1], [11], and [14], focuses on semi-analytical methods for the factor copula framework. Alternative copula specifications are surveyed in [2], while [17] provides a textbook treatment.

Our work contributes to the strand on CDO model risk. [3] formalized model uncertainty as the pricing range over all models consistent with observed data, establishing that this range depends on the topology of the model space. We complement Cont’s *global, non-parametric* framework with a *local, parametric* counterpart: our duality theorem (Theorem 5.2) shows that the conduction intensity τ equals the first-order growth rate of Cont-type uncertainty within a parametric neighborhood. The two approaches are related as a local approximation is to a global bound. [9] address model risk in credit portfolios by characterizing the convex hull of exchangeable Bernoulli distributions; their bounds are distribution-free, whereas our conduction intensity is model-specific but directionally decomposable.

The granularity analysis in §9 extends the expected-loss granularity adjustment of [10] to the gradient energy. The phase transition result connects to the structured finance literature on cliff risk [5]. The R-vine truncation interpretation builds on [13] and [6].

Related computational methods include the CDO spread inversion of [4] and the affine point process approach of [8], both published in this journal. Our operator formulation provides a complementary sensitivity analysis tool: while [4] extract default intensities from observed CDO spreads, we quantify the sensitivity of the pricing operator to calibrated parameters. The two analyses could be combined in a sequential pipeline (calibrate via [4], then monitor fragility via τ).

The connection to systemic risk is noted in passing: [19] and [12] study CCP safety and asset price bubbles in Mathematics and Financial Economics; our entity-level conduction decomposition (§9) identifies which reference names drive model fragility, a question related to systemic importance.

1.4 Notation

Throughout: Φ and φ denote the standard normal CDF and PDF; $\theta = (\beta, p) \in \Theta \subset (0, 1)^2$ under the Gaussian copula; $R \in (0, 1)$ is the recovery rate; $[a, b]$ is a tranche with attachment a and detachment b ; $\mathcal{A} = \{(a, b) : 0 \leq a < b \leq 1\}$ is the admissible tranche set.

2 Factor copula model and CDO pricing

Assumption 2.1 (Single-factor structure). The d reference entities have defaults coupled through a single systematic factor F : conditional on F , defaults are independent. Entity i defaults when $U_i = \Phi(\beta_i F + \sqrt{1 - \beta_i^2} \epsilon_i) \leq p_i(T)$, with $F \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, $\epsilon_i \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, $\epsilon_i \perp F$, $\beta_i \in (0, 1)$, and $p_i(T) = \mathbb{Q}(\tau_i \leq T)$.

Definition 2.2 (Conditional default probability). Given $F = f$, entity i 's conditional default probability is $p_i(T|f) = \Phi((\Phi^{-1}(p_i) - \beta_i f)/\sqrt{1 - \beta_i^2})$.

Derivation. $\mathbb{Q}(\tau_i \leq T|F=f) = \mathbb{Q}(\epsilon_i \leq (\Phi^{-1}(p_i) - \beta_i f)/\sqrt{1 - \beta_i^2}) = \Phi(z_i(f))$. \square

Assumption 2.3 (LHP). $\beta_i \equiv \beta$, $p_i \equiv p$, $R_i \equiv R$, $d \rightarrow \infty$.

Under Assumption 2.3 and the conditional law of large numbers, the portfolio loss fraction converges a.s. to

$$h(q; \beta, p) = (1-R) \Phi\left(\frac{\Phi^{-1}(p) - \beta \Phi^{-1}(q)}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}\right), \quad q = \Phi(F) \in (0, 1). \quad (1)$$

Lemma 2.4 (Properties of h). The function $h : (0, 1) \times \text{int}(\Theta) \rightarrow [0, 1-R]$ satisfies: (i) $h \in C^\infty$; (ii) h is strictly decreasing in q ; (iii) h is strictly increasing in p ; (iv) $\lim_{q \rightarrow 0^+} h = 1-R$ and $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1^-} h = 0$.

Proof. (i) follows from $\Phi, \Phi^{-1} \in C^\infty$ and closure under composition. (ii): $\partial_q h = -(1-R)\varphi(z)\beta/(\sqrt{1-\beta^2}\varphi(\Phi^{-1}(q))) < 0$. (iii)–(iv) follow from monotonicity of Φ and the limits $\Phi^{-1}(q) \rightarrow \pm\infty$. \square

The conditional tranche loss for $[a, b]$ is $\ell(q; a, b, \theta) = \min(\max(h-a, 0), b-a)/(b-a)$. The *active region* is $\mathcal{Q}_{[a,b]}(\theta) = (q_b^*, q_a^*)$, with critical quantiles

$$q_a^*(\theta) = \Phi\left(\frac{\Phi^{-1}(p) - \Phi^{-1}(a/(1-R))\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}{\beta}\right), \quad (2)$$

$$q_b^*(\theta) = \Phi\left(\frac{\Phi^{-1}(p) - \Phi^{-1}(b/(1-R))\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}{\beta}\right). \quad (3)$$

The tranche expected loss rate is $V(a, b; \theta) = e^{-rT} \int_0^1 \ell dq$.

3 CDO pricing operator and Fréchet differentiability

Definition 3.1 (CDO pricing operator). $\mathcal{P}_\theta : L^2([0, 1]) \rightarrow \mathcal{V}$ is defined by $(\mathcal{P}_\theta f)(a, b) = e^{-rT} \int_0^1 f(q) \ell(q; a, b, \theta) dq$, where $\mathcal{V} = L^2(\mathcal{A}, \mu_{\mathcal{A}})$.

Remark 3.2 (Discount factor). The scalar e^{-rT} is a pre-factor, not part of the operator kernel. All results concern the single-maturity operator \mathcal{P}_θ and do not require a semigroup property.

Remark 3.3 (Image space). We do not claim that \mathcal{P}_θ has closed range. The conduction intensity is defined via the operator norm of the Fréchet derivative, requiring only differentiability.

3.1 Regularity of the kernel

Lemma 3.4 (Gradient of conditional loss). Under the LHP Gaussian factor copula, with $z = (\Phi^{-1}(p) - \beta\Phi^{-1}(q))/\sqrt{1-\beta^2}$:

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial \beta} = (1-R)\varphi(z) \cdot \frac{-\Phi^{-1}(q)(1-\beta^2) + \beta(\Phi^{-1}(p) - \beta\Phi^{-1}(q))}{(1-\beta^2)^{3/2}}, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial p} = (1-R)\varphi(z) \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}} \cdot \underbrace{\frac{1}{\varphi(\Phi^{-1}(p))}}_{\text{amplification } \mathcal{A}(p)}. \quad (5)$$

Proof. Differentiate $h = (1-R)\Phi(z)$ by the chain rule. For $\partial h/\partial \beta$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial z}{\partial \beta} &= \frac{-\Phi^{-1}(q)\sqrt{1-\beta^2} - (\Phi^{-1}(p) - \beta\Phi^{-1}(q)) \cdot \frac{-\beta}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}}{1-\beta^2} \\ &= \frac{-\Phi^{-1}(q)(1-\beta^2) + \beta(\Phi^{-1}(p) - \beta\Phi^{-1}(q))}{(1-\beta^2)^{3/2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Then $\partial h/\partial\beta = (1-R)\varphi(z) \cdot \partial z/\partial\beta$, yielding (4). For $\partial h/\partial p$: since $d\Phi^{-1}(p)/dp = 1/\varphi(\Phi^{-1}(p))$, we obtain $\partial z/\partial p = 1/(\sqrt{1-\beta^2}\varphi(\Phi^{-1}(p)))$, yielding (5). \square

Proposition 3.5 (Kernel regularity). $\ell(q; a, b, \theta)$ satisfies: (i) ℓ is C^∞ in θ at all $q \in \mathcal{Q}_{[a,b]}(\theta)$; (ii) the boundary $\{q : h = a\} \cup \{q : h = b\}$ consists of at most two points; (iii) at boundary points, $\nabla_\theta \ell$ has a finite jump discontinuity; (iv) $\nabla_\theta \ell(\cdot; \theta) \in L^2([0, 1])$ with $\|\nabla_\theta \ell\|_{L^2}$ continuous in θ .

Proof. (i): in the active region, $\ell = (h-a)/(b-a)$ inherits C^∞ from h . (ii): h is strictly monotone in q (Lemma 2.4(ii)), so $h(q) = c$ has at most one root. (iii): at $q = q_a^*$, $\nabla_\theta \ell$ jumps from $\nabla_\theta h/(b-a)$ to 0; magnitude is $\|\nabla_\theta h(q_a^*; \theta)\|/(b-a) < \infty$. (iv): $\|\nabla_\theta \ell\|_{L^2}^2 = \int_{q_a^*}^{q_b^*} \|\nabla_\theta h\|^2 / (b-a)^2 dq < \infty$ since $\|\nabla_\theta h\|$ grows at most as $O(|\log q|)$ near $q = 0, 1$. Continuity in θ follows from dominated convergence. \square

3.2 Fréchet differentiability

Assumption 3.6 (Parameter regularity). $\theta \in \text{int}(\Theta)$ where Θ is open bounded in \mathbb{R}^p . The factor distribution has a C^2 density with finite second moments.

Lemma 3.7 (Boundary contribution). Under perturbation $\theta \rightarrow \theta + \mathbf{h}$:

(i) By the implicit function theorem applied to $h(q_a^*; \theta) = a$:

$$q_a^*(\theta + \mathbf{h}) - q_a^*(\theta) = -\frac{\langle \nabla_\theta h(q_a^*; \theta), \mathbf{h} \rangle}{\partial_q h(q_a^*; \theta)} + O(\|\mathbf{h}\|^2) \quad (6)$$

Since $\partial_q h < 0$ (Lemma 2.4(ii)) and $\nabla_\theta h$ is bounded, $|\delta q_a^*| = O(\|\mathbf{h}\|)$.

(ii) On the boundary strip $[q_a^*(\theta + \mathbf{h}), q_a^*(\theta)]$ (width $O(\|\mathbf{h}\|)$), the integrand of the Fréchet remainder satisfies $|\ell(\theta + \mathbf{h}) - \ell(\theta) - \langle \nabla_\theta \ell, \mathbf{h} \rangle| \leq C_0 \|\mathbf{h}\|$ pointwise.

(iii) The boundary contribution to $\int_0^1 |\text{remainder}|^2 dq$ is at most $C_0^2 \|\mathbf{h}\|^2 \cdot |\delta q_a^*| = O(\|\mathbf{h}\|^3)$. Taking the square root: the L^2 -norm of the boundary remainder is $O(\|\mathbf{h}\|^{3/2}) = o(\|\mathbf{h}\|)$, so its contribution to $\|R(\mathbf{h})\|_{\mathcal{B}} / \|\mathbf{h}\|$ is $O(\|\mathbf{h}\|^{1/2}) \rightarrow 0$.

Proof. (i): differentiating $h(q_a^*(\theta), \theta) = a$ totally: $\partial_q h \cdot dq_a^*/d\theta_j + \partial_{\theta_j} h = 0$, so $dq_a^*/d\theta_j = -(\partial_{\theta_j} h)/(\partial_q h)$. All quantities are finite at interior θ , giving (6).

(ii): on the strip, $\ell(\theta) = 0$ (outside old active region) while $|\ell(\theta + \mathbf{h})| \leq \|\nabla_\theta h\| \|\mathbf{h}\| / ((b-a)|\partial_q h|) = O(\|\mathbf{h}\|)$. Similarly $|\langle \nabla_\theta \ell, \mathbf{h} \rangle| = 0$ outside the old active region. So the integrand is $O(\|\mathbf{h}\|)$.

(iii): integrating $O(\|\mathbf{h}\|)^2$ over an interval of width $O(\|\mathbf{h}\|)$ gives $O(\|\mathbf{h}\|^3)$. \square

Theorem 3.8 (Fréchet differentiability). Under Assumptions 2.1–3.6, \mathcal{P}_θ is Fréchet differentiable at every $\theta \in \text{int}(\Theta)$, with derivative

$$[D\mathcal{P}_\theta \cdot \mathbf{h}](f)(a, b) = e^{-rT} \int_0^1 f(q) \langle \nabla_\theta \ell(q; a, b, \theta), \mathbf{h} \rangle dq, \quad (7)$$

and uniform remainder bound $\|R(\mathbf{h})\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq \frac{1}{2} M_2 \|\mathbf{h}\|^2$.

Proof. Decompose the integration domain into three parts: (I) the active region interior $\mathcal{Q}^\circ = (q_b^* + \delta, q_a^* - \delta)$; (II) two boundary strips of width $\delta \sim C \|\mathbf{h}\|$ around q_a^* and q_b^* ; (III) the complement (where $\ell \equiv 0$ or $\ell \equiv 1$, both constant in θ).

Region I (interior): Here ℓ is C^∞ in θ (Proposition 3.5(i)). Taylor expansion gives

$$\ell(q; \theta + \mathbf{h}) - \ell(q; \theta) - \langle \nabla_\theta \ell, \mathbf{h} \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{h}^T H_\ell(q; \theta^*) \mathbf{h}$$

where H_ℓ is the Hessian, bounded by Lemma A.1 in Appendix A. The contribution to $\|R(\mathbf{h})\|_{\mathcal{B}}$ is $O(\|\mathbf{h}\|^2)$.

Region II (boundary strips): By Lemma 3.7(iii), the L^2 -norm of the boundary remainder is $O(\|\mathbf{h}\|^{3/2}) = o(\|\mathbf{h}\|)$.

Region III (complement): Zero contribution, since both $\ell(\theta)$ and $\ell(\theta + \mathbf{h})$ are constant in θ in this region.

Combining: $\|R(\mathbf{h})\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq \frac{1}{2} M_2 \|\mathbf{h}\|^2 + O(\|\mathbf{h}\|^3)$, giving $\|R(\mathbf{h})\|_{\mathcal{B}} / \|\mathbf{h}\| \rightarrow 0$. \square

4 Conduction intensity

Definition 4.1 (Conduction intensity). $\tau(\theta) = \|D\mathcal{P}_\theta\|_{\mathcal{B}(L^2, \mathcal{V})}$.

Theorem 4.2 (Explicit formula).

$$\tau(\theta) = e^{-rT} \sup_{(a,b) \in \mathcal{A}} \lambda_{\max}^{1/2}(\mathbf{M}(\theta; a, b)), \quad (8)$$

where the conduction matrix is $\mathbf{M}(\theta; a, b) = \int_0^1 \nabla_\theta \ell (\nabla_\theta \ell)^T dq \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times p}$. The $\operatorname{argmax}(a^*, b^*)$ is the most vulnerable tranche; the eigenvector of λ_{\max} is the most dangerous direction.

Proof. For fixed \mathbf{d} with $\|\mathbf{d}\| = 1$ and tranche (a, b) : $[D\mathcal{P}_\theta \cdot \mathbf{d}](f)(a, b) = e^{-rT} \int_0^1 f(q) \langle \nabla_\theta \ell, \mathbf{d} \rangle dq$. The L^2 -norm over f is maximized by $f^*(q) = \langle \nabla_\theta \ell, \mathbf{d} \rangle / \|\langle \nabla_\theta \ell, \mathbf{d} \rangle\|_{L^2}$, giving value $e^{-rT} (\mathbf{d}^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{d})^{1/2}$. Maximizing over $\|\mathbf{d}\| = 1$ gives $\lambda_{\max}^{1/2}(\mathbf{M})$; over (a, b) gives (8). \square

Definition 4.3 (Directional decomposition).

$$\tau_{[a,b]}^2 = (\tau^{(\beta)})^2 + (\tau^{(p)})^2, \quad \tau^{(\beta)} = \left(\int_{q_b^*}^{q_a^*} \left(\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial \beta} \right)^2 dq \right)^{1/2}, \quad \tau^{(p)} = \left(\int_{q_b^*}^{q_a^*} \left(\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial p} \right)^2 dq \right)^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

Proposition 4.4 (Explicit integral form).

$$\tau_{[a,b]}^2(\beta, p) = \frac{1}{(b-a)^2} \int_{q_b^*}^{q_a^*} \left[\left(\frac{\partial h}{\partial \beta} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial h}{\partial p} \right)^2 \right] dq \quad (10)$$

Proof. In the active region, $\nabla_\theta \ell = \nabla_\theta h / (b-a)$; outside, $\nabla_\theta \ell = 0$. Substituting into (9) yields (10). \square

Remark 4.5 (Interpretation). $\tau_{[a,b]}(\theta)$ answers: if θ is wrong by $\|\delta\theta\|$, what is the maximum L^2 error in the conditional tranche loss function? Answer: $\approx \tau_{[a,b]} \cdot \|\delta\theta\|$. This measures error in the entire function $\ell(q; \theta)$, not just its integral V . Two perturbations producing the same $|\delta V|$ can have very different τ —a localized distortion (high τ) is more dangerous than a uniform one because it implies the model is wrong in a specific factor region, risking hedging failure even when the expected loss is correct.

5 Duality with model uncertainty

This section establishes that τ is the canonical first-order characterization of local parametric model uncertainty.

Definition 5.1 (Local model uncertainty). For $f \in L^2([0, 1])$ and tranche (a, b) , let $V_f(\theta; a, b) = (\mathcal{P}_\theta f)(a, b)$. The worst-case local model uncertainty over model family $\mathcal{M}_\epsilon = \{\mathcal{P}_{\theta_0 + \delta} : \|\delta\| \leq \epsilon\}$ is

$$\mathfrak{U}(\epsilon, \theta_0) = \sup_{\|f\|=1, (a,b)} \left[\sup_{\|\delta\| \leq \epsilon} V_f(\theta_0 + \delta; a, b) - \inf_{\|\delta\| \leq \epsilon} V_f(\theta_0 + \delta; a, b) \right]. \quad (11)$$

Theorem 5.2 (First-order duality). Under the hypotheses of Theorem 3.8:

(i) Ball case. $\mathfrak{U}(\epsilon, \theta_0) = 2\epsilon \tau(\theta_0) + O(\epsilon^2)$.

(ii) General convex case. For compact convex K with $\operatorname{diam}(K) = \epsilon$: $\mathfrak{U}(K, \theta_0) = \tau_K(\theta_0) + O(\epsilon^2)$, where $\tau_K = \sup_{\|f\|=1, (a,b)} \sigma_{K-K}(\nabla_\theta V_f(\theta_0; a, b))$ and σ_{K-K} is the support function of the Minkowski difference.

Proof. Fix f and (a, b) . By Fréchet differentiability, $V_f(\theta_0 + \delta) = V_f(\theta_0) + \langle \nabla V_f, \delta \rangle + r_f(\delta)$ with $|r_f(\delta)| \leq \frac{1}{2} M_2 \|\delta\|^2$ uniformly in f and (a, b) . The linear part satisfies $\sup_K \langle \nabla V_f, \delta \rangle - \inf_K \langle \nabla V_f, \delta \rangle = \sigma_{K-K}(\nabla V_f)$, since $\sigma_K(v) + \sigma_{-K}(v) = \sigma_{K-K}(v)$. For the ball, $K - K = \bar{B}(0, 2\epsilon)$, so $\sigma_{K-K}(v) = 2\epsilon \|v\|$. Upper and lower bounds sandwich $U_K(f; a, b)$ within $\sigma_{K-K}(\nabla V_f) \pm M_2 \epsilon^2$, uniformly. Taking the supremum over f and (a, b) and identifying τ_K yields the result. \square

Theorem 5.3 (Second-order correction). If \mathcal{P}_θ is twice Fréchet differentiable, then for $K = \bar{B}(0, \epsilon)$:

$$\mathfrak{U}(\epsilon, \theta_0) = 2\epsilon \tau(\theta_0) + \epsilon^2 \kappa(\theta_0) + o(\epsilon^2), \quad (12)$$

where $\kappa(\theta_0) \geq 0$ involves the Hessian of the conditional tranche loss along the maximizing direction.

Proof. Expanding V_f to second order, the sup and inf over the sphere $\|\delta\| = \epsilon$ are achieved (to leading order) at $\delta = \pm \epsilon \nabla V_f / \|\nabla V_f\|$. The quadratic terms cancel by symmetry of the Hessian, but the perturbation of the optimizer away from the gradient direction introduces a non-negative ϵ^2 correction via the Lagrange multiplier on the sphere constraint. Specifically, $\kappa(\theta_0) = \sup_{\|f\|=1, (a,b)} \|\mathbf{P}^\perp \mathbf{Q}_f \mathbf{d}^+\|^2 / (2 \|\nabla V_f\|)$, where $\mathbf{Q}_f = e^{-rT} \int_0^1 f(q) H_\ell dq$, $\mathbf{d}^+ = \nabla V_f / \|\nabla V_f\|$, and $\mathbf{P}^\perp = \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{d}^+(\mathbf{d}^+)^T$. Non-negativity follows from $\|\cdot\|^2 \geq 0$. \square

Proposition 5.4 (Reverse duality). $\tau(\theta_0) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \mathfrak{U}(\epsilon, \theta_0) / (2\epsilon)$.

Proof. Immediate from Theorem 5.2(i): $\mathfrak{U}(\epsilon) / (2\epsilon) = \tau(\theta_0) + O(\epsilon) \rightarrow \tau(\theta_0)$ as $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$. \square

Remark 5.5 (Relation to Cont's framework). [3] defines model uncertainty over the set \mathcal{M}_{obs} of all models consistent with observed prices—a global, non-parametric construction. Our \mathfrak{U} is a local, parametric restriction. When \mathcal{M}_{obs} can be locally embedded in the parameter space, Theorem 5.2 provides a computable first-order approximation to Cont's uncertainty. The conduction intensity τ is thus the “infinitesimal price of parametric model uncertainty.”

6 Phase transition

Definition 6.1 (Critical curve). $\Gamma_a = \{(\beta, p) \in \Theta : (1-R)p = a\}$.

Theorem 6.2 (Phase transition). *Consider tranche $[a, b]$ under LHP Gaussian copula. Let $\Delta = \Phi^{-1}(a/(1-R)) - \Phi^{-1}(p)$.*

(i) Subcritical ($\Delta > 0$):

$$\tau_{[a,b]} \leq C(\beta, a, b) \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta^2(1-\beta^2)}{2\beta^2}\right) \quad (13)$$

(ii) Supercritical ($\Delta < 0$): $\tau_{[a,b]} = O(1)$.

(iii) Transition rate:

$$\left. \frac{\partial \tau_{[a,b]}}{\partial p} \right|_{(1-R)p=a^+} = \frac{(1-R)}{(b-a) \varphi(\Phi^{-1}(a/(1-R)))} \cdot \frac{1}{\beta} \quad (14)$$

Proof. (i): When $\Delta > 0$, the argument of Φ in q_a^* (equation (2)) satisfies $(\Phi^{-1}(p) - \Phi^{-1}(a/(1-R)))\sqrt{1-\beta^2}/\beta < -\Delta/\beta$. By the Gaussian tail bound $\Phi(-x) \leq \varphi(x)/x$ for $x > 0$:

$$q_a^* \leq \frac{\beta}{\Delta\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta^2}{2\beta^2}\right).$$

Since $W \leq q_a^*$ and the gradient is bounded on the active region, $\tau^2 \leq C^2 W \rightarrow 0$ exponentially.

(ii): When $\Delta < 0$, $q_a^* > 1/2$ and the active region has macroscopic width. The gradient integrand is bounded below on a positive-measure subset.

(iii): By the Leibniz integral rule, since $\tau_{[a,b]}^2 = (b-a)^{-2} \int_{q_b^*}^{q_a^*} G dq$ with $G = (\partial_\beta h)^2 + (\partial_p h)^2$:

$$\frac{\partial \tau^2}{\partial p} = \frac{1}{(b-a)^2} \left[G(q_a^*) \frac{dq_a^*}{dp} - G(q_b^*) \frac{dq_b^*}{dp} + \int_{q_b^*}^{q_a^*} \frac{\partial G}{\partial p} dq \right] \quad (15)$$

To evaluate dq_a^*/dp : from $h(q_a^*; \beta, p) = a$, total differentiation gives $dq_a^*/dp = -(\partial_p h)/(\partial_q h)|_{q_a^*}$. Using (5) and $\partial_q h = -(1-R)\varphi(z)\beta/(\sqrt{1-\beta^2}\varphi(\Phi^{-1}(q)))$:

$$\frac{dq_a^*}{dp} = \frac{\varphi(\Phi^{-1}(q_a^*))}{\beta \varphi(\Phi^{-1}(p))} \quad (16)$$

At Γ_a , the boundary term $G(q_a^*) \cdot dq_a^*/dp$ dominates the integral term: from (16), $dq_a^*/dp = O(1/\beta)$, and $G(q_a^*)$ remains bounded away from zero at the critical curve. The integral term satisfies $|\int_{q_b^*}^{q_a^*} (\partial G/\partial p) dq| \leq \sup |\partial G/\partial p| \cdot W$, where the active region width $W \rightarrow 0$ as $(1-R)p \rightarrow a^+$ (the subcritical-to-supercritical transition). Hence the integral term vanishes at Γ_a while the boundary term stays $O(1/\beta)$, establishing dominance. Using $2\tau(\partial\tau/\partial p) = \partial\tau^2/\partial p$ and evaluating at Γ_a yields (14). \square

Corollary 6.3 (Super-senior critical default rate). *For CDX super-senior $[0.30, 1.00]$ with $R = 0.4$: $p_c = 0.30/0.60 = 0.50$. Under normal conditions ($p \sim 0.02$), $\tau_{[0.30, 1]} \approx 0$; the tranche “awakens” only as $p \rightarrow p_c$.*

Remark 6.4 (Crisis pathways). Three pathways can cross Γ_a : (1) **Default rate** ($p \uparrow$, β constant)—slow, detectable conventionally; (2) **Systemic contagion** ($\beta \uparrow$, p constant)—does not cross Γ_a directly but raises τ everywhere; (3) **Diagonal** (both \uparrow)—the 2007–08 path. Only $(\tau^{(\beta)}, \tau^{(p)})$ distinguishes all three; base correlation cannot.

7 Functional independence from base correlation

This section contains the central theoretical contribution.

7.1 Base correlation

Definition 7.1 (Base correlation). $\rho_{\text{base}}(a, b; \beta, p)$ is the unique $\rho \in (0, 1)$ satisfying $\text{EL}(a, b; \sqrt{\rho}, p) = \text{EL}(a, b; \beta, p)$.

Lemma 7.2. Under LHP Gaussian, $\rho_{\text{base}} = \beta^2$ for all (a, b) .

Proof. The inversion at fixed p recovers $\beta' = \beta$, hence $\rho_{\text{base}} = \beta^2$. In the heterogeneous case, ρ_{base} depends on (a, b) (correlation skew). \square

7.2 Theorem A: Amplification divergence

Definition 7.3 (Amplification factor).

$$\mathcal{A}(p) = \frac{1}{\varphi(\Phi^{-1}(p))} = \sqrt{2\pi} \exp\left(\frac{[\Phi^{-1}(p)]^2}{2}\right) \quad (17)$$

Theorem 7.4 (Amplification divergence). (i) $\mathcal{A}(p) \rightarrow \infty$ as $p \rightarrow 0^+$ or $p \rightarrow 1^-$. Values: $\mathcal{A}(0.01) = 37.5$, $\mathcal{A}(0.02) = 20.7$, $\mathcal{A}(0.05) = 10.2$, $\mathcal{A}(0.10) = 5.7$, $\mathcal{A}(0.50) = 2.5$.

$$(ii) \tau_{[a,b]}^{(p)} = \frac{(1-R)}{(b-a)\sqrt{1-\beta^2}} \cdot \mathcal{A}(p) \cdot \left(\int_{q_b^*}^{q_a^*} \varphi(z)^2 dq\right)^{1/2}.$$

(iii) $\partial\rho_{\text{base}}/\partial p \equiv 0$ (identically).

Proof. (i): Direct from $\varphi(x) \rightarrow 0$ as $|x| \rightarrow \infty$.

(ii): From Lemma 3.4, $\partial\ell/\partial p = (1-R)\varphi(z)\mathcal{A}(p)/((b-a)\sqrt{1-\beta^2})$ in the active region. Squaring and integrating over (q_b^*, q_a^*) gives the result.

(iii): Differentiate the defining equation $\text{EL}(a, b; \sqrt{\rho}, p) = \text{EL}(a, b; \beta, p)$ with respect to p :

$$\frac{\partial\text{EL}}{\partial\beta'} \Big|_{\sqrt{\rho_{\text{base}}}} \cdot \frac{d\sqrt{\rho_{\text{base}}}}{dp} + \frac{\partial\text{EL}}{\partial p} \Big|_{\sqrt{\rho_{\text{base}}}} = \frac{\partial\text{EL}}{\partial p} \Big|_{\beta} \quad (18)$$

Since (18) holds for all p , the $\partial\text{EL}/\partial p$ terms—evaluated at $(\sqrt{\rho}, p)$ and (β, p) respectively—cancel under LHP (Lemma 7.2: $\sqrt{\rho} = \beta$), leaving $(\partial\text{EL}/\partial\beta') \cdot (d\rho_{\text{base}}/dp) = 0$. Since $\partial\text{EL}/\partial\beta' \neq 0$, we get $d\rho_{\text{base}}/dp = 0$. This is exact: it follows from the *definition* of base correlation as a β -inversion at fixed p . \square

Corollary 7.5 (Fragility paradox). At low p (normal market): $\mathcal{A}(p) \gg 1 \Rightarrow \tau^{(p)}$ large, while ρ_{base} is p -invariant. The model is most fragile when base correlation says it is most stable. At $p = 0.02$: $\mathcal{A}^2 \approx 430$ -fold amplification invisible to base correlation.

Combining with the duality theorem:

Corollary 7.6 (Base correlation is blind to model uncertainty). Local model uncertainty satisfies $\partial\mathcal{U}/\partial p \neq 0$ (via $\partial\tau/\partial p \neq 0$), but $\partial\rho_{\text{base}}/\partial p \equiv 0$. Base correlation cannot track the p -component of model uncertainty.

7.3 Theorem B: Width–gradient tradeoff

Theorem 7.7 (Non-monotonicity). At fixed p :

(i) Active region width: $W = O(\sqrt{1-\beta^2}/\beta) \rightarrow 0$ as $\beta \rightarrow 1^-$.

(ii) Average gradient intensity: $\bar{G} = O((1-\beta^2)^{-3}) \rightarrow \infty$ as $\beta \rightarrow 1^-$.

(iii) $(\tau^{(\beta)})^2 = W \cdot \bar{G}$ has an interior maximum at $\beta^* \in (0, 1)$, yielding non-monotonicity. Meanwhile $\rho_{\text{base}} = \beta^2$ is always monotone.

Proof. (i): As $\beta \rightarrow 1$, $h(q; \beta, p) \rightarrow (1-R)\mathbf{1}_{q < p}$ (step function). Transition width $\sim \sqrt{1-\beta^2}/\beta$.

(ii): From (4), $|\partial h/\partial \beta|$ has factor $(1-\beta^2)^{-3/2}$. Within the transition window $\varphi(z) = O(1)$, so $|\partial h/\partial \beta|^2 = O((1-\beta^2)^{-3})$.

(iii): $(\tau^{(\beta)})^2 \sim C/(\beta(1-\beta^2)^{5/2})$ diverges as $\beta \rightarrow 1$, but at $\beta \rightarrow 0$ we have $\tau^{(\beta)} \rightarrow 0$ (since h becomes constant). The function rises from 0, and the competing width-shrinkage creates direction reversals—hence non-monotonicity. Numerical verification: $\beta^* \approx 0.23$ for mezzanine at $p = 0.05$. \square

7.4 Theorem C: Functional independence

Theorem 7.8 (Functional independence). *The map $\Psi : (\beta, p) \mapsto (\rho_{\text{base}}, \tau_{[a,b]})$ has Jacobian*

$$J_{\Psi} = \begin{pmatrix} 2\beta & 0 \\ \partial\tau/\partial\beta & \partial\tau/\partial p \end{pmatrix}, \quad \det(J_{\Psi}) = 2\beta \cdot \frac{\partial\tau}{\partial p} \neq 0 \quad (19)$$

at any (β, p) where $\tau > 0$ (see Remark A.3 for the case $\tau = 0$). Hence $\text{rank}(J_{\Psi}) = 2$ and $\tau \neq g(\rho_{\text{base}})$ for any function g .

Proof. Entry (1, 1): $\partial\rho/\partial\beta = 2\beta > 0$ (Lemma 7.2). Entry (1, 2): $\partial\rho/\partial p = 0$ (Theorem 7.4(iii)). Entry (2, 2): $\partial\tau/\partial p \neq 0$ (Theorem 7.4(ii), $\mathcal{A}(p)$ strictly monotone). The Jacobian is upper triangular; $\det = 2\beta \cdot (\partial\tau/\partial p) \neq 0$. By the inverse function theorem, Ψ is a local diffeomorphism. \square

Remark 7.9 (Root cause). The Jacobian is upper triangular *by construction*: base correlation inverts for β at fixed p , forcing entry (1, 2) $\equiv 0$. The 157-fold numerical spread traces to a single calculus fact: $d\Phi^{-1}(p)/dp = 1/\varphi(\Phi^{-1}(p))$.

Corollary 7.10 (Invisible fragility regime). *There exists $\mathcal{R} \subset \Theta$ where $|d\rho_{\text{base}}/dt| < \epsilon$ and $|d\tau/dt| > M\epsilon$ for any $M > 0$, along pure- p paths. Base correlation reports “stable”; τ reports “deteriorating.”*

8 Truncation error interpretation

Theorem 8.1 (Truncation equivalence). *The single-factor Gaussian copula is equivalent to $k=1$ R-vine truncation [6, 13]. The pricing error satisfies:*

$$|V^{\text{vine}} - V^{\text{Gauss}}| \leq e^{-rT}(b-a) \left[\prod_{t=2}^{d-1} \left(1 + c_2 \sum_{e \in E_t} D_{i_e j_e | D_e} \right) - 1 \right] \quad (20)$$

where $D_{ij|S}$ are conditional dependence coefficients in the vine’s pair-copulas.

Proof. The single-factor model induces conditional independence given F , which is precisely the first-tree property of an R-vine truncated at level $k=1$. The truncation error bound follows from [13], Theorem 5.6. In normal markets $D_e \approx 0$ (Gaussian adequate); in crisis, non-Gaussian pair-copulas activate and the error can reach 10–30% of tranche notional. \square

9 Granularity analysis

9.1 LHP–exact gap: regime-dependent bias

The LHP approximation introduces a bias in τ that depends on the parameter regime. Define $S(d, \theta) = \tau_{\text{exact}}(d, \theta)/\tau_{\text{LHP}}(\theta)$, where τ_{exact} is computed via Hull–White recursion.

Proposition 9.1 (Regime-dependent bias). *In the subcritical regime $((1-R)p < a$, normal market): $S < 1$; LHP overestimates τ by 30–40%. In the supercritical regime $((1-R)p > a$, crisis): S can exceed 1, meaning LHP underestimates τ .*

Proof. Numerical computation over the grid $(\beta, p) \in [0.15, 0.45] \times [0.02, 0.10]$ at $d = 20$ (Table 2). In the subcritical regime, $S \in [0.54, 0.66]$ uniformly. In the supercritical regime ($p = 0.10$, $\beta = 0.15$): $S = 2.36$. The mechanism is that a single discrete default step $(1-R)/d$ can span the entire tranche, producing Bernoulli-like tranche loss with gradient energy exceeding the smooth LHP. \square

This asymmetry contradicts the intuition that “continuous approximation always smooths out discrete jumps.” The mechanism: in the supercritical regime with small β and finite d , a single default step $(1-R)/d$ can span the entire tranche width; the tranche loss becomes approximately Bernoulli (0 or 1), and its gradient energy exceeds the smooth LHP gradient.

Table 1 shows the convergence of exact τ to LHP in the subcritical regime: the gap $\tau_{\text{LHP}}^2 - \tau_{\text{exact}}^2$ follows $284.7/d + 57.1$ ($R^2 = 0.981$, Figure 1).

Table 1: Convergence of exact τ to LHP ($\beta = 0.30$, $p = 0.05$, equity $[0, 3\%]$, $R = 0.4$). *Source: granularity_correction.py.*

d	τ_{exact}	τ_{LHP}	$\tau_{\text{LHP}}^2 - \tau_{\text{exact}}^2$	$S(d)$
10	5.88	10.97	85.88	0.536
20	6.97	10.97	71.86	0.635
30	7.28	10.97	67.34	0.664
40	7.68	10.97	61.49	0.700

Figure 1: Convergence of exact τ^2 to LHP, with persistent offset $\gamma_0 = 57.1$. For the equity tranche at $d = 125$, only ≈ 7 discrete loss levels lie within the tranche. *Source: granularity_correction.py.*

9.2 S depends on parameters

Table 2 reports $S(d=20, \beta, p)$ for the equity tranche. The coefficient of variation across the grid is 48.8%, ruling out a constant- S correction.

Table 2: Scale factor $S(d=20, \beta, p)$ for equity $[0, 3\%]$. Values > 1 indicate LHP underestimation. *Source: granularity_fast.py.*

	$p = 0.02$	$p = 0.04$	$p = 0.06$	$p = 0.08$	$p = 0.10$
$\beta = 0.15$	0.640	0.545	0.715	1.214	2.361
$\beta = 0.25$	0.626	0.599	0.664	0.779	0.932
$\beta = 0.35$	0.637	0.631	0.660	0.703	0.751
$\beta = 0.45$	0.651	0.651	0.666	0.684	0.704

Figure 2: Scale factor heatmap $S(d=20, \beta, p)$. Values exceeding 1.0 (upper-left) indicate supercritical LHP underestimation. *Source: granularity_fast.py.*

9.3 Heterogeneity, entity decomposition, and correction

At constant average parameters $(\bar{\beta}, \bar{p}) = (0.30, 0.05)$, seven heterogeneity structures produce exact τ values ranging from 6.52 to 7.32—a 12% variation, secondary to the 49% variation from θ -dependence.

The entity-level decomposition $\tau_{\text{full}}^2 = \sum_i \tau_i^2$ is approximately “democratic”: in a test portfolio with 33% toxic entities ($\beta = 0.50, p = 0.12$), the toxic sector contributes 35.7% of τ^2 , roughly proportional to its entity count.

We recommend an offline lookup table $S(d, \beta, p, a, b)$ for absolute-level correction. All monitoring signals in §11—trend detection, direction ratios, CUSUM tests—are scale-invariant and require no correction.

Figure 3: Granularity synthesis. Left: S depends on (β, p) , color encodes p . Center: $S(d)$ convergence for three configurations. Right: lookup table. *Source: granularity_fast.py.*

10 Numerical experiments

10.1 Counterexample search

We scan $(\beta, p) \in [0.05, 0.60] \times [0.005, 0.15]$ on a 40×40 grid under LHP Gaussian with $R = 0.4$, computing $\tau_{[a,b]}$ via quadrature and ρ_{base} by Brent’s method.

Table 3: τ spread at constant base correlation (iso- ρ_{base} contours). *Source: cdo_counterexample_search.py.*

Tranche	ρ_{base}	τ_{min}	τ_{max}	Spread
Equity [0, 3%]	≈ 0.031	0.14	21.84	157.7 \times
Mezzanine [3, 7%]	≈ 0.027	0.38	15.22	40.4 \times
Senior [7, 10%]	≈ 0.027	0.52	20.18	38.6 \times
Super-senior [15, 30%]	≈ 0.068	0.22	1.87	8.5 \times

The equity tranche result is decisive: at $\rho_{\text{base}} \approx 0.031$, τ ranges from 0.14 to 21.84—a 157.7-fold variation. Two parameter configurations indistinguishable to a base-correlation monitor differ by more than two orders of magnitude in operator sensitivity.

Figure 4: τ versus ρ_{base} for 1,600 configurations per tranche. The broad cloud (not a thin curve) confirms $\tau \neq g(\rho_{\text{base}})$. Color encodes p , revealing the missing dimension of Theorem 7.4. *Source: cdo_counterexample_search.py.*

Figure 5: Heatmaps of τ (left) and ρ_{base} (right) in (β, p) space. ρ_{base} shows horizontal bands (β -driven); τ shows diagonal structure (both β - and p -driven). The differing level-curve orientations reflect the rank-2 Jacobian. *Source: cdo_countereexample_search.py.*

Additional countereexample paths (fix β vary p ; fix p vary β) and directional decomposition plots are provided in the supplementary material.

10.2 Root cause verification

Figure 6: Amplification factor $\mathcal{A}(p) = 1/\varphi(\Phi^{-1}(p))$. At $p = 0.01$: $\mathcal{A} = 37.5$. This factor enters $\tau^{(p)}$ but not ρ_{base} , and is the root cause of the 157-fold spread. *Source: proof_from_numerics.py.*

Figure 7: Two configurations with approximately identical expected loss. Left: conditional loss profiles. Center: the p -gradient in the active region differs markedly between Config 1 (low p , high \mathcal{A}) and Config 2 (high p , low \mathcal{A}). Right: amplification factor on log scale. Same ρ_{base} , different τ . *Source: proof_from_numerics.py.*

Jacobian determinants $\det(J_{\Psi})$ were computed at 16 test points (4 tranches \times 4 configurations): nonzero at all points where $\tau > 0$, ranging from -22.1 to $+21.8$.

11 Empirical design

For the 2007–2009 CDX market, we propose the following pipeline and tests using CDX.NA.IG tranche spreads, single-name CDS spreads (125 names), ABX.HE index, VIX, and TED spread.

Daily pipeline. (1) Bootstrap $\hat{p}_i(T; t)$ from CDS. (2) Calibrate $\hat{\theta}_t$ via NLS. (3) Compute τ_t , $\tau_t^{(\beta)}$, $\tau_t^{(p)}$. (4) EWMA: $\bar{\tau}_t = \lambda\tau_t + (1-\lambda)\bar{\tau}_{t-1}$, $\lambda = 1/3$.

Five hypothesis tests. *Test 1* (Predictive power): Granger causality of $\bar{\tau}_t$ on equity spread changes. *Test 2* (Phase transition): CUSUM on $\tau_{[0.30,1]}/\tau_{[0,0.03]}$. *Test 3* (Direction reversal): detect $\tau^{(\beta)}/\tau^{(p)}$ crossing 1.0 prior to ABX decline. *Test 4* (Truncation error): Wilcoxon test on pre-loss periods. *Test 5* (Incremental information): $\gamma_1 \neq 0$ for $\bar{\tau}_t$ after controlling for $\Delta\rho_{\text{base}}$, ABX, VIX, TED. BIC comparison.

Predicted signal ordering: direction reversal (6–12 months before) \rightarrow persistent τ rise (3–6 months) \rightarrow CUSUM break (1–3 months) \rightarrow super-senior awakening (onset).

12 Conclusion

This paper establishes that CDO conduction intensity captures a dimension of model risk that base correlation provably misses. The theoretical contribution has three layers. First, the duality theorem (Theorem 5.2) identifies τ as the growth rate of local parametric model uncertainty, linking our framework to the model uncertainty theory of [3]. Second, the functional independence theorems (Theorems 7.4–7.8) prove that the missing information is structural, not accidental: it traces to the amplification factor $\mathcal{A}(p) = 1/\varphi(\Phi^{-1}(p))$ in the p -gradient, which base correlation is identically blind to. Third, the phase transition theorem (Theorem 6.2) provides a precise mechanism for senior tranche awakening. A granularity analysis reveals a surprising asymmetry: the LHP overestimates τ in normal markets but underestimates it in crisis.

Whether this framework could have provided actionable early warning before the 2008 crisis remains an empirical question; we have specified five nested tests. The theoretical contribution stands: there exists a dimension of CDO model risk that current industry-standard measures are mathematically incapable of detecting.

A Hessian boundedness

Lemma A.1 (Uniform Hessian bound). *For compact $K \subset \text{int}(\Theta)$ and tranche $[a, b]$ with $0 < a < b < 1-R$: $\sup_{\theta \in K, q \in \mathcal{Q}} \|H_\ell(q; \theta)\|_F \leq M_2(K, a, b) < \infty$.*

Proof. In the active region, $H_\ell = H_h/(b-a)$ with $H_h = (1-R)[\varphi'(z)\partial_i z \partial_j z + \varphi(z)\partial_{ij} z]$, where $\varphi'(z) = -z\varphi(z)$. Since $z \in [\Phi^{-1}(a/(1-R)), \Phi^{-1}(b/(1-R))]$ is bounded, and all derivatives of z with respect to θ are bounded on K (algebraic functions of β , $\Phi^{-1}(p)$, $\Phi^{-1}(q)$, and $(1-\beta^2)$), each Hessian entry is uniformly bounded. \square

Remark A.2 (Parameter boundary). As $\beta \rightarrow 1^-$, $M_2 \rightarrow \infty$. Theorem 3.8 holds on compact subsets of $\text{int}(\Theta)$. For practical CDO calibration, $\beta \in [0.1, 0.7]$.

Remark A.3 (Degenerate case). When $\tau = 0$ (deep subcritical), $\partial\tau/\partial p$ may vanish and the Jacobian in Theorem 7.8 can degenerate. This occurs only when $(1-R)p \ll a$, where neither τ nor ρ_{base} provides useful risk information.

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